

ECO-CONSCIOUS THINKING IN ELT: MERGING ECOLINGUISTIC INSIGHTS WITH GREEN TEACHING APPROACHES

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Abstract. *This article analyzes the concepts of Eco linguistics and “green pedagogy” from the perspective of the need to integrate them into the process of foreign language teaching. It is argued that language teachers can form not only linguistic competencies in students, but also ecological awareness, social responsibility, and sustainable thinking through ecological texts, discussions and assignments. An analysis of the views of the research scientists shows that the concept of “green pedagogy” combines language learning with ecological values as a modern, innovative, and sustainable approach to foreign language teaching.*

Keywords: *green pedagogy, ecological education, sustainable development, language teaching, ecological awareness, Eco linguistic competence.*

Introduction. In recent years, global climate change, environmental problems, and sustainable development issues have become increasingly important in the field of education. The 21st century education system aims not only to give knowledge, but also to form ecological awareness, responsible attitudes, and sustainable thinking. In this context, Eco linguistics — as a science that studies the interrelationships between language, culture, and the environment — opens up new perspectives in language education.

Language teachers are important mediators in communicating global issues — climate justice, resource stewardship, and the balance between humans and nature — to students. Therefore, using ecological texts, discussions, and assignments in foreign language teaching not only develops students' linguistic competence, but also their environmental literacy and social responsibility.

Research methods and materials. This article aims to determine the effectiveness of increasing students' ecological awareness in ELT classes through integrating language and ecology issues, in particular, Eco linguistics, in teaching foreign languages, and was conducted in a combination of qualitative and quantitative approaches. That is, theoretical analysis - scientific sources, foreign and local literature, and best practices on eco-conscious thinking in language classes was studied, analyzed, and summarized.

Discussions and findings. R. Alexander explains that integrating Eco linguistics into the education system, and in particular into English language teaching, will allow for a deeper understanding and focus on sustainability issues. By incorporating Eco linguistic approaches into the curriculum, teachers can encourage students to critically analyze linguistic expressions of the environment and consider the impact of their language use on environmental consciousness. This approach to education is consistent with the broader goals of UNESCO's Education for Sustainable Development (ESD), which aims to enable learners to make informed decisions and take responsible actions for ecological integrity, economic viability and a just society. [2;5;10;].

According to Yildirim and Aytan the concept of “green” pedagogy is an educational approach that focuses on sustainability and environmental awareness. This approach is considered a revolutionary, innovative and modern method in the field of language teaching due to its unique characteristics. “Green” pedagogy combines environmental awareness with language skills and aims to develop not only the linguistic potential of language learners, but also to form the knowledge, attitudes, worldview and actions necessary to solve the environmental crises they face today. [11]

Omnia Latif Ibrahim Abdel Latif emphasizes that GELT (Green English Language Teaching) is beneficial for teachers and students and involves a multi-faceted approach. GELT helps students connect different fields of knowledge, enhance their learning experience, and develop critical thinking. It encourages students to analyze environmental issues and develop a sense of responsibility in them. GELT also helps students understand the international nature of environmental issues and encourages them to adopt a sustainable worldview. Teachers can integrate environmental topics into language teaching methodologies and create curricula that include sustainability topics. This helps students learn about environmental issues through language learning. Teachers should design lessons that include descriptive writing on environmental topics, use multimedia resources, and implement assessment strategies that assess students' language skills and understanding of environmental issues. Students should write essays or create presentations on environmental topics, and participate in community projects that promote environmental protection. By adopting the principles of GELT, teachers, mentors, and students can together contribute to raising an environmentally literate generation [12].

In general, teaching English not only teaches the language, but also educates people who are aware and active in the fight against climate change. Barber et al. argue that climate education is about changing the way we do things, as well as seeing our daily decisions and actions through “environmental eyes.” This approach can also be applied to English language lessons and materials. It is noted that the following are aspects to consider when incorporating sustainability topics into education:

- Integrating sustainability topics into the curriculum

Lessons on the climate crisis are a good opportunity to raise awareness of sustainability among students. However, it can sometimes be difficult to dedicate an entire lesson to this topic, given the curriculum, coursework, and exams. Therefore, the question of how to integrate climate and sustainability topics into the curriculum is important.

For example, if the “transportation” section of a textbook contains text about different modes of travel, students can be encouraged to think about how each mode of transport affects the environment. This can help to discuss the carbon footprint of air and car travel, as well as eco-friendly options such as cycling and walking. These small changes do not significantly change the length of the lesson, but they do introduce the topic of climate.

- Taking into consideration the age and level of the learners

Some scientific topics should be age- and cognitively appropriate. Young language learners need support in understanding the connection between global warming and events such as flooding in the region.

"Eco-anxiety" is a major issue among adolescents: social media can spread a lot of negative information about the climate crisis. Therefore, it is recommended to spread the idea that the emphasis should be on solutions, not problems, and that even small changes can make a difference.

- Managing the level of students' knowledge

When introducing the topic of climate for the first time, it can be difficult to measure students' technical knowledge. For this, it is recommended to conduct a small quiz in an informal, discussion-based way. Learning scientific knowledge together between the teacher and students can also reduce mutual anxiety. With younger students, it is better to explain the topic using everyday examples such as plastic bags or traffic pollution.

- Opportunities for cross-curricular integration

Climate change and sustainability issues can be taught in many subjects: geography, biology, social studies, history, sports. For example, when water scarcity is discussed in English, students will understand better if the same topic is also discussed in biology. Therefore, cross-curricular cooperation is important.

- The role of English lessons in making schools "green"

Many educational institutions around the world are changing their activities to be more environmentally friendly: recycling paper, using solar energy, planting trees. Incorporating the topic of climate change into the lesson is part of this process. For example, students can create a small garden in the school or make posters about plastic pollution, which can strengthen the lesson. [13]

In conclusion, it is worth noting that the use of "green" pedagogy in teaching English not only develops language competencies, but also shapes students as environmentally conscious, socially responsible individuals. This approach turns language learning into a meaningful, modern, and sustainable development process.

Below, we analyze the reasons and descriptions given by a number of researchers and scholars for why "green pedagogy" or environmental education should be integrated into foreign language lessons (see Table 1).

Table 1.

Reasons for integrating "green pedagogy"/environmental education into foreign language lessons

Researchers/scientists	Reasons
Goatly	The main goal of combining environmental education with language teaching is to teach the practical application of the language and at the same time to provide various activities on environmental issues [3].
Tang	The aim of environmental education is to educate students of English as a foreign language about global environmental issues. Issues such as deforestation, climate change, pollution, food production and biodiversity loss should be a core component of ELT lessons. This should be done at primary, secondary and tertiary levels [9].
Nkwetisama	English language teaching cannot be considered successful if students are unaware of global issues, including environmental threats. It is necessary to include environmental topics in the language teaching process [8].

Mliless M., Larouz M.	Environmental education (EE) educates students to be environmentally responsible by instilling the environmental values and conscious behaviors necessary to prevent environmental degradation.[6]
Hauschild S., Poltavtchenko E., Stoller F.L.	By incorporating environmental education into the language teaching process, students can be introduced to current issues, taught to create a healthy, sustainable world, and developed language skills [4].
Muldagalieva A.A., Okusheva G.T., Orazbekova I.G.	Environmental education is an integrative approach that can be implemented in various disciplines and professions. Language courses provide an effective opportunity to teach about environmental issues, develop dependence on nature, critical thinking, awareness, and environmental sensitivity [7].
Al Karasneh et al.	In today's era of increasing ecological crisis, education is an important tool for shaping sustainable thinking and developing a deep understanding of environmental issues in students [1].

What is the climate justice movement? There are many definitions, but at its core, climate justice is the recognition that environmental change is not just a natural problem, but also a social and political one. Unfortunately, not everyone contributes equally to environmental and climate problems, and their consequences are not equally shared. While environmental change affects everyone, it affects the poorest people, women, and other disadvantaged groups first and hardest. Recognizing this disparity and taking action to protect the environment while addressing racism, inequality, and prejudice is what climate justice is all about.

Conclusion. In conclusion, the integration of the Eco linguistic approach and "green pedagogy" into foreign language education is one of the most important tasks of the modern education system. Through this approach, students not only learn the language, but also form a responsible position towards global environmental problems. The development of Eco linguistic competencies strengthens critical and reflective thinking in students, encourages a creative approach, and educates them as global citizens committed to the values of environmental sustainability, justice, and humanity. The principles of "green" pedagogy make the learning process more meaningful, interdisciplinary, and close to life.

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